

Optimal Temperature and Duration for Dabbing Customers with the Massage Compressed Packs Reported from Customers' Perception

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Abstract : The objective of this research was to study the appropriate thermal level and time for dabbing customers with the massage compressed pack reported from their perception. The investigation was conducted by comparing different angles of tilted heads done by the customers together with their perception before and after the dabbing. The variables included different temperature of the compressed packs and different dabbing duration. Samples in this study included volunteers who got massage therapy and dabbing with hot compressed packs by traditional Thai medical students. The experiment was conducted during January to June 2013. The research tool consisted of angle meters, stop watches, thermometers, and massage compressed packs. The customers were interviewed for their perceptions before and after the dabbing. The results showed that: 1. There was a difference of the average angles of tilted heads before and after the dabbing. 2. There was no difference of the average angles at different temperatures but constant duration. 3. There was no difference of the average angles at different durations. 4. The customers reported relaxation no matter what the various temperatures and various dabbing durations were. However, they reported too hot at the temperature 70 °C and over.

Keywords : massage, therapy, therapeutic systems, technologies

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